

A NOVEL COMB JOINT CONCEPT FOR HIGH STRENGTH UNIDIRECTIONAL CARBON FIBRE BONDED JOINTS

A.Towse¹, KD Potter¹, MR Wisnom¹ and RD Adams²

¹ *Department of Aerospace Engineering, University of Bristol, Queen's Building, University Walk, Bristol, BS8 1TR, UK.*

² *Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Bristol, Queen's Building, University Walk, Bristol, BS8 1TR, UK*

SUMMARY: This paper describes a novel concept for achieving high joint strengths at low cost by a comb joint approach. An advantage of the joint is scalability, where a number of these joints can be stacked to meet the requirements at much lower weight, cost and risk than a single very long and heavy joint. An analysis was carried out where mechanical loads were applied to a generic fully restrained element of a comb stack, and the resulting strains were superimposed on the residual strain state resulting from thermal cooldown from cure temperature. The technique was then extended to a three comb stack (3x1mm carbon strips), where it was seen that the joint strength would be expected to be 3.2kN/mm. A full-size demonstrator was built utilising the same design philosophy as presented above, the resulting failure gave a joint strength of 6.64kN/mm, a failure load in excess of any previously seen adhesive joint.

KEYWORDS: adhesive joints, high load intensity, comb joint, finite element analysis, thermal stresses.

INTRODUCTION

The theoretical performance advantage of using high strength carbon fibre in unidirectional form has been well known and accepted for many years. However, the problems begin when attempting to utilise such materials in structures due to the difficulty of jointing. The preferred solution is to utilise adhesive bonding in a number of different geometries, such as single lap, double lap, stepped or scarf joints. The first suffers from low joint strengths measured in terms of N/mm of joint width, whilst the latter pair are stronger but at much greater cost and process risk. Even the strongest double-lap joints peak at around 3kN/mm.[1] It would be possible to design a long shallow scarf joint to take out large loads, but the cost and weight of such a joint would become prohibitive for large loads. An alternative approach is presented here, in that multiple strong and simple double lap joints are stacked to form a compact weight efficient joint, capable of carrying the high loads by splitting the load through the members in the comb. In this fashion, the joint need now only be marginally longer than the overlap of each joint. Furthermore, the comb joint solution has inherently greater redundancy and resistance to damage, as the central comb members are protected by the outer members, in every case but an edge-wise impact.

GENERIC COMB GEOMETRY

Previous work [1,2] has been focused on pushing the limits of performance from double and single lap joints. For well known reasons, this has concentrated primarily on designing the end 10% of the overlap well, and ensuring they are manufactured to high quality to ensure good strength values. This has been very successful, although it has been acknowledged throughout that these joints may involve difficulty to manufacture. This is especially true at the rear, or blind, end of the joint where it is initially difficult to produce a spew fillet, and secondly it is very difficult to gain access to this point to inspect the resultant geometry. For this reason, this paper has used a realistic rear geometry that is simple to manufacture and requires no rear spew fillets. The manufacturing procedure would be to trim to size, surface treat (grit blast) and assemble before adhesive injection. The geometry is as shown schematically in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Front and rear comb joint geometry

It should be noted that although spew fillets and reverse tapers have been seen to be beneficial [1], the best results would come from an extremely sharp adherend tip. This would be expensive to machine as well as being sensitive to damage during manufacture or repair. The joints in this report deal with finite tip thicknesses of 0.2mm which is castable (HP turbine blades are routinely cast to this thickness in Ti) and practical.

FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

To gain an understanding of the failure load and mode of the comb joints in question, a non-linear analysis was carried out using the ABAQUS FEA suite of software, including the effects of material non-linearity and residual thermal strains from cure. To that end, an adhesive stress-strain curve was gained from previous work [3] for the Permabond ESP110 two-part Aluminium filled adhesive (RT properties).

Quadratic quadrilaterals using the plane strain assumption were used throughout the model, with quadratic triangles where necessary. The yield criterion used was von Mises, in preference to the more rigorous Raghava criterion. It was found that the difference in failure load prediction for the joints between the two criteria was within the scatter one could expect in experimental tests, and therefore the more robust von Mises was chosen. The unidirectional CFRP was modelled as 924C-T800, with $E_x=170\text{GPa}$, $E_y=10\text{GPa}$, $\nu_{xy}=0.27$ and $G_{xy}=7\text{GPa}$. The epoxy modulus to yield was linear and with a value of 3.83GPa with $\nu=0.38$. The post-yield behaviour was modelled as in Fig. 2. The titanium properties were $E_{Ti}=110\text{GPa}$ and $\nu_{Ti}=0.3$.

Stress - Strain curve for ESP110

Fig. 2: ESP110 stress-strain curve

The failure criterion that was applied was the critical strain at a distance criterion. The distance chosen was 0.19mm, which was calibrated from previous tests using this adhesive system on end-tab specimens. The experimental failure load was observed, and the required distance for the prediction to match the experiment was determined. However, there is an added complication with this joint, in that at the rear of the joint there is no clear indication in which direction to apply the criterion. Ideally, it should be critical strain at a distance in any direction, as the nature of the strain distribution around the singularity was not circular. Therefore, a criterion of critical strain at a radius was chosen, with the same distance as before. Consequently, it is accepted that this strain at a distance may not be applicable to strain at a radius, and therefore the predictions may be inaccurate. The FEA will, however, also give qualitative information on the likely failure mode and location of the joint. The final geometry of the comb models is as shown in Fig 3.

Fig. 3: Single and three comb stack, showing plane of symmetry

SINGLE COMB ELEMENT

To gain an understanding of the performance of a comb element which is deep within a large stack (utilising a monolithic metallic node), it was decided to analyse a single comb element, as shown schematically in Fig. 3b). The loads and boundary conditions that were applied to this model are as shown below in Fig. 4. A symmetric boundary condition was applied to the bottom edge of the model, with the nodes along the top edge coupled to move by the same

distance in 'y' due to thermal or mechanical loading. A face pressure, incrementally stepping up to 1.5GPa tension was applied at the free end of the carbon. For the thermal loading, all the nodes were given an initial temperature of 120°C (T_g of the adhesive), and allowed to cool with the same boundary conditions as the mechanical load to 20°C, giving a total δT of 100°C.

Fig. 4: Single comb element boundary conditions, with constraint equation

By repeating linear runs, with and without the constraint along the top edge, it was seen that differing levels of hydrostatic stress were induced in the epoxy, resulting in lower von Mises stress (higher hydrostatic) for the constrained model than for the unconstrained model. It was apparent, therefore, that more yielding would occur on the outer elements of a large stack of elements due to the lower hydrostatic constraint, hence failure could reasonably be expected to occur from the outer elements first.

The single comb element model was then subjected to a full non-linear analysis, including the effect of residual thermal stresses set up by cooling from cure. The criterion of strain at a radius was applied, both at the front and the rear, including the constraint equation. The results are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1: Strength predictions for single comb element

Adhesive failure strain	Stress in T800 at failure (GPa)	Failure location	Joint strength (N/mm)
3.3%	1.20GPa (0.69% ϵ)	Top of front fillet	1200

It can be seen that the joint strength (in N/mm terms) is not high, although considering the nature of the geometry at the rear end, and the requirement for manufacturability at the front (finite tip thicknesses), the strengths are reasonable. The failure mode was by epoxy cracking from the tip of the Titanium adherend at the front of the joint.

The biggest advantage of the comb joint is its stacking ability. For example, if the requirement was for a 5kN/mm joint, we would need to stack up at least 4 elements to achieve this. As will be seen later, this stacking does not follow such a linear relationship. A further point of note is the effect of the hydrostatic stress state close to failure of the joint. By definition, this will induce a high through-thickness tensile stress (peel) on the unidirectional CFRP, which could induce a second failure mode of peel in the central combs of a large stack if epoxy cracking did not occur first.

THREE COMB STACK

These models are more indicative of a real joint, as no assumed constraint needs to be applied to model the joint deformation. The loads and boundary conditions are as shown in Fig. 5. The method of thermal and mechanical load application is the same as that described previously.

Fig. 5: Three comb stack boundary condition showing mechanical load

The thermal load resulted in an overall deformation and shrinkage of the joints, with the resultant stresses and strains driven primarily by the high CTE of the epoxy. This resulted in some localised yielding of the adhesive around the sharp edges of the model, both at the rear and in the front spew fillet. However, the situation is somewhat different to the single comb element analysed previously in that no assumed displacement profile has been applied, i.e. no constraint equation is used. By comparison of the deformations present in the three comb stack with those forced by the constraint equation in the constrained single comb element, it was seen that the deformations in the three comb stack were different than the constrained model, resulting in lower hydrostatic stress and therefore more yielding and lower failure loads than would have been achieved with three fully constrained single comb elements.

Therefore the single comb model is the strongest, and will probably be indicative of the centre comb element(s) in a large stack of, say, 10 or more elements. However, the outer elements are not subject to the same constraint from their neighbours, and we can expect failure to occur from the outermost elements in the stack, assuming no differences in assembly. The primary reason for this extra constraint in the centre is due to the 1.7mm thick Ti strip that separates the inner and outer comb elements. Under thermal or mechanical tensile/ loading compressive, forces act on this strip in an attempt to bend it due to thermal or Poisson contraction. However, the thickness of this strip in comparison to the thickness of the outermost strip of Ti means they have greatly differing bending stiffness. The cube law of bending means that this centre thick strip has 8x the stiffness of the outer one, and therefore deforms less and shields the inner epoxy layer from large deformation. This increases the σ_y component, although not to the levels seen in the single comb model with applied constraint, and results in greater hydrostatic and lower von Mises stress. This is backed up by the failure load predictions for the three comb stack, as presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Strength predictions for three comb stack

Adhesive failure strain	Stress in T800 at joint failure (GPa)	Failure location	Joint strength (N/mm)
3.3%	1.066GPa (0.61% ϵ)	Outer comb element, front adhesive fillet, exposed tip	3198

The governing failure location is the front of the joint, at the outside comb element at the enclosed corner giving a total joint strength of 3198 N/mm, although failure is almost equally likely from the front or rear of the joint, the front being only marginally worse. It is likely, therefore, that for a more ductile adhesive capable of more than 3.3%, the failure would be controlled by the geometry at the rear of the joint, and measures such as altering the stiffness blend between inner and outer adherends would seem appropriate. It is also clear that the model analysed here does not behave in the same way as three single comb elements. For

three fully constrained single comb elements, the strength would be 3600N/mm, versus 3198N/mm for the three comb stack. This is due to the constraint factors mentioned earlier. For comparison, a prediction for a double lap joint with 3mm central CFRP adherend and 1.5mm CFRP outer adherends using the same load, adhesive and similar geometry was found to be 2200N/mm, including thermal effects. This joint used the reverse taper and spew fillet at both ends, and would therefore be more complex to manufacture, as well as being 31% weaker than the three comb stack joint, using the same amount of carbon. The double lap joint is, however, a much lighter joint than the Titanium three comb stack (approx. 4.8g for T800 double lap joint, neglecting adhesive compared to c.19.4g for Titanium 3 comb stack, also neglecting adhesive). The trade-off between material cost, assembly cost, process risk, weight and load carrying capacity between the carbon double lap joint and the three comb stack is beyond the scope of this paper. What is clear, however, is that by splitting the single 3mm thick carbon adherend into three parts, the operating strain can be increased from 0.42% for the double lap joint to 0.61% for the three comb stack, with the corresponding increase in load.

PRACTICAL TEST

After the completion of the above analysis, a test on a 5 comb stack joint of similar dimensions to the analysed geometry was undertaken. The adhesive used was not ESP110, as parallel work on double lap joints suggested that the 3M 3448 paste adhesive is superior in RT and hot/wet performance to ESP110. Furthermore, 3448 does not present the problems associated with bonded carbon to Aluminium-filled epoxy.

A five comb stack was tested under tensile load, the failure occurring at 6.64kN/mm by cohesive failure in the adhesive from the tip of the Titanium adherend, as predicted. It is not possible to state from which element of the stack the failure originated, as the post-failure load redistribution and energy release caused damage and failure to all the fillets throughout the stack.

DISCUSSION

It is clear from the results that the fully constrained single comb model represents a very idealised element, and will only be indicative of a comb element which is at or close to the centre of a large stack of elements. How deep this stack must be to mimic this constrained condition has not been investigated. It is also apparent, that this centre comb (and indeed all the elements not at the outside edges) have lower principal strains due to their higher constraint. Therefore, the two outer comb elements are the most likely to initiate failure and are the most likely to sustain in-service damage. It would be prudent to devote more time to NDT and inspection of these outermost elements as they represent the weakest link in the joint. This is a fortunate situation, as detailed inspection of central elements will present many problems in practice.

The single comb element, with full constraint, generates large through-thickness (peel) stresses in the carbon due the presence of a significant hydrostatic stress state. Therefore, although the central comb elements have a lower chance of failure from epoxy cracking, for very deeply embedded comb elements there is an increased chance of this second failure mode causing delamination deep within the joint. If this presents itself to be a problem with large stack joints, then it would be required to split the joint into two (say from one 14 comb

stack to two seven comb stacks). This would reduce the constraint at the centre and reduce the chance of delamination.

It is apparent then, that a method for carrying large loads through the use of a relatively simple adhesively bonded joint has been proven. However, the practical use of such an arrangement still requires some thought. For example, the stability of such a stack of thin laminate sheet under compressive loads is likely to be very poor indeed. Consequently, some linkage between the elements will be required, a light foam or honeycomb would seem the most likely candidate. The baseline for this analysis has concentrated on the Titanium adherend being a monolithic block, from which the required shapes are removed, probably via the use of a tapered mill and slotting saw. It is possible, however, to stack up multiple double lap joints to achieve a similar result.

CONCLUSIONS

Both single comb elements and three comb stacks have been analysed, and it has been shown that, for these geometries, failure is expected to be initiated from the outermost elements at the front of the joint. The strength prediction for the three comb stack in comparison to a prediction for a single CFRP double lap joint with a 3mm central adherend and 1.5mm carbon outer adherends can be seen to be higher, 3.198kN/mm for the three comb stack cf. 2.2kN/mm for the double lap joint. The practical test of a five comb stack has demonstrated the capability of carrying 6.64kN/mm (16.9 tons/inch) with a purely adhesively bonded joint. It also demonstrates the ability of utilising high-strength unidirectional material to carry high loads at moderate strains without the normal problems associated with the jointing.

In conclusion, the comb joint concept is a good candidate where high load transfer is required, such as a highly loaded anchorage or tether. It also has the ability for easy scaling up to meet the required load, simply by adding more elements, although the relationship between number of elements and final joint strength is not linear. Care must be taken with large stacks as delamination could be seen in the central elements.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to acknowledge the support of the UK Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council, via contract number GRK66833.

REFERENCES

1. Adams R.D., Atkins R.W., Harris J.A. & Kinloch A.J. "Stress analysis and failure properties of carbon-fibre reinforced plastic/steel double lap joints", *J. Adhesion* **20** 1986, 29-53
2. Tsai M.Y. & Morton J. "The effect of a spew fillet on adhesive stress distributions in laminated composite single-lap joints", *Composite Structures* **32** (1995) 123-131
3. Grant L.D.R., "The characterisation of adhesive joints found typically in the automotive industry" PhD thesis, University of Bristol, (1994)